

after transplanting with a hand-operated sprayer.

Thrips populations were counted with 5 sweeps/plot using a plastic bat 20 cm in diameter, 48 h after spraying. All treatments significantly reduced thrips intensity (see table). Neem oil at 2% was as effective as insecticides in controlling rice thrips. □

Infection of brown planthopper (BPH) with insect fungi in the laboratory

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The BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is commonly infected with insect fungi (Deuteromycotina; Hyphomycetes) in the field and in insect rearing cages. The fungi can be isolated on artificial media and mass-produced in liquid fermentation media. To select the most virulent fungus species or strain for BPH control on rice, we bioassayed selected isolates.

We tested infection of BPH by *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill., *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metsch.) Sorokin, *M. flavoviride* var. *minus* Rombach, Humber and Roberts, and *Hirsutella citriformis* Speare (see table).

Fungi isolated from insects were grown on Emerson's YpSs agar (Ma, Mfm), and Sabouraud dextrose agar (Bb, Hc). Conidia were washed off plates in a 0.02% Tween 80 solution after 2 wk of incubation at 25-28 °C. Conidia were counted by standard hemocytometer techniques, and

Abbreviations of fungal species and strains.

Fungus species	Strain
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	BbE
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	Ma12
	Ma16
<i>M. flavoviride</i> var. <i>minus</i>	Mfm11
	Mfm16
<i>Hirsutella citriformis</i>	Hc490

suspensions of 10^2 to 10^8 conidia/ml prepared by serial dilution in the Tween 80 solution.

Each treatment had 50 BPH alates. Insects were dipped in conidia suspension in Tween 80 (0.02%), submerged for 60 s, and transferred to filter paper to drain off liquid. Insects of the control treatment were dipped in pure Tween 80 (0.02%) solution before transfer. The insects were kept on potted rice plants in mylar cages in a greenhouse at 25-30 °C (day) and 15-20 °C (night), with humidity near

saturation.

After 5 d of incubation, live and infected (dead and covered with fungus) insects were counted and mortality calculated:

Mortality (%) = $100 \times ((\text{no. infected insects})/(\text{no. infected insects} + \text{no. living insects}))$

Mortality in the fungus treatments was corrected for control mortality (8%) by Abbott's formula.

Results showed mortality increased with increasing dosage, but did not differ among fungi. □

Effect of Dimilin (R) and Dipel (R) on leaffolder (LF) larvae

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Rice LF (Pyralidae: Lepidoptera) infests irrigated rice in Southeast Asia. Broad-

spectrum insecticides sprayed to control LF larvae can also kill such natural enemies as predators (mainly spiders) and parasites. That can lead to outbreaks of secondary pests, such as brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål).

Selective insecticides kill only target pests. We tested Dimilin^(R), containing diflubenzuron, a chitin inhibitor, and the *Bacillus thuringiensis* product Dipel^(R)

Mortality (%)

Mortality of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* populations caused by Dimilin (Dim) and Dipel (Dip) treatments, IRRI, 1988. Vertical lines on bars represent standard deviations.

for selective LF control in the greenhouse.

Because sprays do not reach larvae in folded leaves as well as they do larvae on fresh, unfolded leaves, we compared spray effectiveness before and after leaf folding.

Pots of 24 rice plants (3

pots/ treatment) were randomly infested with 25 2d- to 3d-instar larvae of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée. Insecticides were applied either just before infestation or 1 d after infestation, when more than 90% of larvae had folded leaves. After 3 d, living and dead larvae were counted.

Treatment before leaf folding was more effective than treatment after folding (see figure). All treatments except Dip b1 and Dip a1 differed significantly from control. Dimilin was more effective than Dipel, but not always significantly so. □

Weed management

Weed control in direct seeded rice under puddled condition

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In samba 1985 in Chingleput district, weed control treatments were compared in irrigated direct seeded CO 43 rice under puddled condition. There were 7 weedicide treatments, 1 farmer's method of weeding on 20 and 40 d after seeding (DAS), and an unweeded control in a randomized block design with 4 replications (see table).

The farmer's method of hand weeding 20 and 40 DAS gave highest grain yield of 3.9 t/ha, on par with butachlor at 1.0 kg ai/ha plus 1 hand weeding in 40

Economics of weed control treatments on irrigated direct seeded CO 43 rice variety.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1985 samba.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Yield increase		Weed dry wt (g/m ²) at 40 DAS	Weed control (%)	Cost (\$/ha)	Savings (\$/ha)
		t/ha	%				
Unweeded control	3.2	—	—	160	—	—	—
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DAS	3.9	0.7	20	41	75	36	—
Butachlor 1.0 kg ai/ha	3.7	0.5	15	40	75	—	—
2,4-D EE 0.8 kg ai/ha	3.5	0.3	9	47	71	17	19
Fluchloralin 1.0 kg ai/ha	3.5	0.3	9	42	74	—	—
Piperophos 1.0 kg ai/ha	3.7	0.5	14	38	76	—	—
Butachlor 1.0 kg ai/ha + 1 hand weeding	3.9	0.7	20	35	78	25	10
Oxyfluorfen 0.1 kg ai/ha	3.7	0.5	14	39	76	17	19
Oxadiazon 0.5 kg ai/ha	3.7	0.5	14	59	63	17	19
LSD	0.1						

^aA dash = data not available.

DAS. These yields were 0.7 t/ha (20%) more than that of the control.

The weed dry matter 40 DAS was least with butachlor application plus 1 hand weeding (35 g/m²), or 78% better than that of the control. The farmer's hand weeding gave 75% more weed

control.

Thus, in direct sown rice under puddled condition, butachlor plus 1 hand weeding can control weeds and produce yields as well as can 2 weeding with manual labor, saving \$10/ha in weeding cost. □

Unrecorded weed hosts for rice blast (BI) pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in India

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In India, weeds such as *Leersia hexandra*, *Panicum repens*, *Arundo donax*, *Brachiaria mutica*, and *Cyperus compressus* have been reported to harbor *P. oryzae*.

During 1986-87, we searched for weed hosts of *P. oryzae* in Manipur ricefields, field bunds, and irrigation channels. We collected diseased weeds in districts of Imphal, Thoubal, Bishenpur, Churachandpur, and Senapati.

Rice reaction to *P. oryzae* isolates from 4 weed hosts. Manipur, India, 1986-87.

Weed host	Disease reaction ^a on	
	HR-12	KD, 2-6-3
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	+	+
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	+	+
<i>C. compressus</i>	+	—
<i>C. iria</i>	+	+

^a+ = infected, — = noninfected.

From these collections, we isolated *P. oryzae* on potato dextrose agar. To test pathogenicity, we sprayed mycelial fragments of the isolated fungus, prepared from 7-d-old culture, onto weed hosts. Weeds sprayed with sterile water served as control.

Among the weed hosts, *L. hexandra*, *C. compressus*, *Cyperus rotundus*, and

C. iria consistently harbored *P. oryzae*. The occurrence on *C. rotundus* and *C. iria* constitutes a first report from India.

To study pathogenicity, we raised highly susceptible HR-12 and popular, high-yielding KD, 2-6-3 in pots and inoculated seedlings at 3-4 leaf stage with different isolates of *P. oryzae*. All isolates produced BI symptoms on HR-12. Only the isolate from *C. compressus* failed to infect KD,2-6-3 (see table). □

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